

Material Challenges and Alloy Selection for Particle/s-CO₂ Heat Exchangers in Concentrated Solar Power Systems

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Combining supercritical CO₂ (s-CO₂) cycles with particle-based heat transfer media for concentrated solar power (CSP) plants offers great potential if the material challenges can be overcome. The core challenge in integrating these systems is the particle/s-CO₂ heat exchanger, which must handle extreme conditions, such as high temperatures, high pressures, and erosion from both CO₂ and hot particles. The mechanical requirements for such a heat exchanger are exceedingly high, demanding materials that can resist CO₂-corrosion and high stresses due to the operating conditions in the supercritical fluid. In addition, the heat exchanger material must also withstand severely erosive conditions due to the hot heat-carrying particles sliding on the outside of the tube walls. The best selection of an appropriate heat exchanger alloy is discussed, considering cross-references from supercritical and ultrasupercritical steam boilers and supercritical CO₂ cycles in nuclear power applications. A method is shown to estimate the mechanical requirements, as well as the challenge of determining the corrosion and erosion allowance. Ultimately, the material requirements and challenges are summarized for creating a practical and durable heat exchanger to support the integration of supercritical CO₂-based cycles with CSP plants. Future research and material testing are defined to overcome the final hurdles.

areas (e.g., 1.3 million square meters for a 150 MWe plant)^[1] that concentrate solar radiation and focus it on a receiver. In a conventional Rankine steam cycle, the heat transfer medium (commonly a molten salt) in central receiver plants transmits the energy to steam, which is then used to produce electricity via a turbine and generator system. A vital advantage of these plants is the availability of thermal energy storage (via the molten salts) to keep the electricity production running throughout the night. Therefore, a key advantage of CSP systems compared to fluctuating renewables, such as wind and photovoltaic, is that this technology can reliably and continuously provide dispatchable, renewable energy for half the cost of comparable photovoltaic systems with battery storage.^[2,3] This CSP technology could be even more valuable and competitive by going to higher operating temperatures to achieve higher thermal efficiency. Therefore, many researchers worldwide are working on developments to enable higher temperatures than those available in the current

1. Introduction

Concentrated solar thermal power (CSP) plants will be an integral piece of the energy production sector of a carbon-neutral, green energy future. CSP technologies are based on large mirror

commercial plants (390 °C for thermo-oil and 560 °C for molten salt). The higher heat transfer medium temperatures would also facilitate the coupling of solar energy to innovative chemical or metallurgical technologies such as producing “solar fuels,” aluminum recycling, solar water treatment, seawater desalination, or synthesis of chemicals.^[4]

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DOI: 10.1002/adem.202402060

Generally, two media are currently being investigated to operate the solar receiver at temperatures above 1000 °C: air and solid particles. Solid ceramic particles offer the advantage of being directly used as the thermal storage media. However, the movement and handling of such hot particles impose severe material challenges due to the high temperatures and abrasive effects. In such designs, the crucial component from a materials perspective is the heat exchanger, where the thermal energy is harvested from the hot particles and transferred to convert water into steam and drive a turbine, just as in a conventional plant.

Although employed for decades, this steam or Rankine cycle remains inefficient and water intensive. Compared to steam, supercritical carbon dioxide (s-CO₂) offers many advantages with the so-called Brayton cycle.^[5] In this cycle, the s-CO₂ does not require the additional energy input needed for phase transformations (evaporating liquid to gas or condensing gas to liquid). Also,

Figure 1. Integration of a CSP particle system into highly efficient s-CO₂ Brayton power cycles for electricity production.^[56]

s-CO₂ has a higher mass and physical density at the relevant temperatures than steam. Thus, less working fluid and a smaller overall system size are required for an equivalent energy conversion. As a significant drawback, the demands on the materials in contact with the hot s-CO₂ are also higher. When this Brayton cycle is combined with the particle CSP technology, the alloy or material solution must accommodate highly demanding operating conditions, requiring sufficient high-temperature strength and erosion resistance due to the hot heat-carrying particles sliding on the exterior tube walls. Simultaneously, the interior of the HEX tubes must withstand oxidation and carburization from supercritical CO₂.

Such harsh conditions constitute an immense challenge for material selection, and providing a suitable solution is a worthwhile undertaking for materials science, considering the multitude of benefits that would arise from the integration of a highly efficient s-CO₂ Brayton power cycle into a particle-based CSP system, as outlined in **Figure 1** for the next generation of CSP plants. The present paper aims to review, discuss, and utilize the information currently available in the literature to inform the selection of materials for such conditions and predict their yearly metal loss.

2. Component Design and Heat Exchanger

Different designs have been suggested for CSP particle/s-CO₂ heat exchangers, which can be distinguished according to their flow pattern: “packed bed,” “fluidized bed,” or “granular flow”^[6–8] and are still constantly improved.^[9] Their advantages and disadvantages are comprehensively discussed in ref. [10] The following is focused on the “granular flow” design, meaning the particles flow around a bundle of tubes. This design is characterized by high particle mixing and intense particle-wall contact, guaranteeing high thermal transfer and highly erosive conditions.

2.1. Mechanical Requirements for Material Selection

Regarding mechanical properties, the tubes in the bundle in the “granular flow” design have high-stress requirements due to the

s-CO₂ flow, which requires temperatures of up to 750 °C and about 25–30 MPa internal pressure. This drastically limits the possible choice of materials and points toward expensive precipitation-hardened nickel-based alloys. To make matters more complex, beyond the circumferential stress, CO₂ corrosion and oxidation and erosion, along with oxidation, will occur on the interior and exterior of the tubes, respectively. The particles under discussion for such plants are all ceramic particles, classically used for grinding or blasting purposes, such as sand, alumina, silicates, hematite, or even silicon carbide.^[11,12] This alone highlights the severity of such an application. In addition to the erosion caused by the heat-carrying particles, the external surface of the heat exchanger tubes must withstand high-temperature oxidation (up to about 900 °C). In contrast, the inner surface of the tubes needs to withstand simultaneous oxidation and carburization due to the supercritical CO₂. Meanwhile, the bulk of the tube material must carry the mechanical stress of the supercritical conditions and other thermally induced stresses, e.g., due to the heterogeneous surface temperature distribution on the external side of the tube caused by the nonuniform particle velocity pattern. According to these complex conditions, there is no simple material selection criteria. A list of crucial operating parameters such as s-CO₂ temperature ≥650–750 °C along with an outer wall temperature ≥850–900 °C and an internal pressure ≥25 MPa have been identified within the project COMPASsCO₂. These values must be met to achieve the efficiency improvements targeted in this project and make this technology competitive. In the following sections, these requirements will be discussed in terms of the s-CO₂ HEX conditions and the available commercial alloys that have the potential to meet the selection criteria.

For the materials selection, the operational and mechanical requirements will be dealt with simultaneously as they are strongly interconnected and cannot be easily separated. The best references for the mechanical requirements for particle-based CSP plants are publications that refer to reference materials from supercritical and ultra-supercritical steam boilers, supercritical CO₂ cycles in nuclear power applications, and standard CSP

plants with steam or molten salt as a heat-carrying medium. A review of current materials used in supercritical (SC) and ultra-supercritical (USC) fossil plants (traditional Rankine cycle) and of new materials for advanced-USC shows that the requirements there have much in common with the demands on heat exchanger tube materials for particle-based CSP, e.g., ref. [13]. The CSP-HEX tube materials must operate above 650 °C at elevated internal tube pressures of ≥ 25 MPa. Reasonably thin-walled components with good heat transfer emphasize the necessity to select a material with a high allowable stress. The sources mentioned above provide an initial set of materials for consideration. These high-temperature materials can be classified according to their operating temperature ranges. The most advanced 9–12 wt% chromium steels have a temperature limit of ≈ 650 °C, and the highest temperature austenitic alloys now reach ≈ 700 °C, although in many works, 680 °C is given as their temperature limit. Solid solution-strengthened Ni-based alloys also reach operating temperatures up to ≈ 700 °C, while age-hardened Ni-based alloys can be used in temperatures up to 760 °C.^[14,15] The second most significant factor in the selection of the materials is the price. With the relative costs of the 9–12 Cr wt% steels set to one, advanced austenitic steels come in at 2–5 times more, while the Ni-based alloys fall in the range of 20–25 times the cost of a ferritic-martensitic solution.^[16,17]

Generally, both fossil and CSP plants have high temperatures and pressurized tubing in common. They must be built and constructed according to international codes and standards such as the American Society of Mechanical Engineers (ASME) Boiler and Pressure Vessel (B&PV) Codes. To select alloys to meet such rigorous standards, the most adequate existing criteria are the European and American directives for pressure applications. These directives both use creep strengths for rapid validation of the required mechanical properties but show slight differences in the values due to the differences in value extrapolation techniques. The European Pressure Equipment Directive (PED) bases the pressure calculation on the average creep value extrapolated to 10 000 h. In contrast, the ASME uses the maximum allowable stress values derived from the nominal creep values. This maximum allowable stress criteria for the temperature limitations of these different classes of alloys are based on the rupture lifetime of 100 000 h at 100 MPa (which equals the approximate stress value at which the pipe wall thickness can be kept thin enough to minimize the potential for thermal fatigue cracking). The ASME directive is more restrictive for applying austenitic steels and is therefore used hereafter in this work.^[13] For the CSP application, the differences are not critical in the case of Ni-based alloys, which vastly exceed the required stresses. Still, they can be significant in the case of austenitic steels, which can be pushed to the limit of the allowed stresses. Among the austenitic grades, Sanicro 25 shows the highest values of the qualified commercial alloys and is even higher than IN617 for temperatures up to ≈ 620 °C.^[18] The age-hardened alloy 740 and Haynes 282 are in a league by themselves, as seen in **Figure 2**.

The HEX tube wall thickness can be calculated for a given outer diameter using Barlow's formula based on the maximum allowable stress and internal pressure. This equation is discussed in detail in the ASME B31.1, 2022 (Power Piping Code).^[19] The version in the code is a derivate of Barlow's formula but also

takes weldings, for example, and experience with different material classes into account

$$t = \frac{P * D}{2(SEW + PY)} - CR \quad (1)$$

In this equation, t is the minimum thickness, P is the design pressure, D is the outside diameter, and SE is the maximum allowable stress. W is a welding parameter (taken as 1), and Y (here 0.7) is a coefficient explained in detail in ASME B31.1 (Power Piping Code). The variable CR in the equation is a placeholder for the corrosion or erosion rate or allowance. The allowable stress is essential in these calculations because higher allowable stress enables thinner walls, which will ensure lower heat loss, better cyclic flexibility, and lower costs.

Assuming a tube design is required for the granular flow design, Equation (1) enables the determination of the application temperature range and limits for tubes of different alloys and steels. The high-strength ferritic-martensitic steel P92 is stronger than P91 and maintains a maximum allowable stress of 38.3 MPa even at 650 °C (Figure 2). Assuming an outer diameter of 40 and internal pressure of 25 MPa, it would result in a large wall thickness of 12.64 mm, according to Equation (1). It is critical to avoid larger wall thicknesses as larger wall thicknesses reduce the mechanical stress in the material from internal pressure while simultaneously increasing the thermal gradient and thermal stresses and thus decreasing the thermal fatigue life. As a rule of thumb from the ASME code, the wall thickness should never exceed 1/6 of the outer diameter so that the thermal stresses do not become critical. For the heat exchanger, an outer diameter is assumed to be 40 mm, with an internal pressure of 25 MPa, so that the maximum allowable stress must be above a value of ≈ 65 MPa (ASME code, Figure 2). This ≈ 65 MPa limit is shown as S_{\min} in Figure 2. This criterion is fulfilled for all materials except P91 and P92 (even at 650 °C). The strengths can be reflected in the required wall thicknesses at 700 °C: Sanicro 25–6.0 mm; alloys 617 and 625–4.9 mm; and alloy 740 and Haynes 282–3.1 mm. The differences between alloy 617 and alloy 625 and alloy 740 and Haynes 282, in further digits, are not visible at the scale illustrated in **Figure 3**, which shows the considerable differences in necessary metal, following an illustration suggested by Tortorelli et al.^[20]

So far, the calculated minimum wall thickness required allowances for corrosion and erosion have been ignored, which need to be added to address metal wastage using the CR term when looking toward a lifetime prediction of the tube. ASME B31.1 states that “the thickness of this allowance is in the designer's judgment and should be consistent with the expected life of the piping.” This is a key question for the application of the HEX for a particle CSP receiver, where not only is corrosion allowance a key factor due to high-temperature corrosion during exposure to supercritical CO₂ on the interior but also oxidation and erosion on the outside occur, which is reviewed in the following sections for the various potential alloys. This is a critical value because the total wall thickness for the given example must not exceed the thermal fatigue life limit according to code of 6.6 in the example here.

Figure 2. Maximum allowable stresses for different steels and Ni-based alloys from 600 to 760 °C according to ASME standard B31.1 following.^[13,18]

Figure 3. Required wall thicknesses for different materials for a 40 mm \varnothing tube with 25 MPa internal pressure at 700 °C: Sanicro 25–6.0 mm; alloys 617 and 625–4.9 mm; alloy 740 and Haynes 282–3.1 mm.

From this mechanical property discussion, alloys with a maximum allowable stress above Sanicro 25 are the only option for operation at 700 °C for a s-CO₂/particle HEX.

2.2. High-Temperature Corrosion (in CO₂)

As mentioned, the internal and external walls need to be considered in terms of degradation and corrosion rates. At the internal

wall of the heat exchanger, the tube material must withstand s-CO₂. Supercritical CO₂ can cause fast breakaway oxidation in 9–12 wt% Cr ferritic martensitic steels, but also accelerated corrosion in alloys such as alloy 316 or 800 (at 650 °C and 20 MPa), compared to oxidation in air.^[21,22] Pint et al. showed that a critical Cr threshold is a prerequisite for a large variety of Fe- and Ni-based alloys in s-CO₂, and alloys with less than 18 wt% cannot be considered for long-term applications.^[23] Generally, at the target temperature of 700 °C for alloys that fulfill this criterion, the weight gains in s-CO₂ are relatively low. However, some Fe-based materials can suffer from internal carburization.^[24–27] Detailed studies of several aspects of CO₂ corrosion have been conducted in many laboratories, and most of the data can be found in the work of Pint and co-authors from Oak Ridge National Laboratory.^[21–23,28–36] It should be noted that many of those publications show the same set of data.

The corrosion/erosion rate allowance is crucial for designing the particle/s-CO₂ HEX tubes, which will operate in s-CO₂ and thus at elevated pressures. The influence of pressure on scale formation and mass change kinetics must be considered to estimate such a value. The studies that investigated the temperature and pressure influence on CO₂ exposure tests reveal that the equipment of the laboratories, especially the autoclave setup, flowing or stagnant gas, and the CO₂ purity strongly influenced the corrosion results.^[37]

Despite the more recent testing efforts, the data remain limited at the relevant temperature range between 650° and 750 °C.

The upper temperature included in this paper is slightly above the targeted heat exchanger temperature range for the CSP particle receiver tubes identified by COMPASsCO₂. Still, it gives a sound indication of the differences in the behavior of the potential commercial alloys. In **Figure 4–6**, weight gain data from different literature have been collected, as exemplified for 650, 700 °C (all available data), and 750 °C (alloy 617). RG denotes research grade CO₂ and ID industrial grade CO₂. From this plots, the oxidation rates can be calculated.

Generally, it can be seen that the data for the different alloys follow a parabolic behavior (linear behavior in such plots). It is interesting to note that the straight-line equation does not intersect with the zero point in many cases. While this can be explained with different heating-up procedures, it does not play a significant role in the industrially relevant long-term behavior. It can also be seen that for the alloys of interest, the values are generally in a similar range.

Figure 4. Weight gain data for 650 °C of Sanicro 25, Alloy 617, and Alloy 625 in different CO₂ grades.

Figure 5. Weight gain data at 700 °C from different sources for the various alloys.

Figure 6. Weight gain data at 750 °C exemplified for alloy 617.

2.2.1. Kinetics of High-Temperature Corrosion in CO₂

The rate constants or k_p values can be calculated for the different alloys and temperatures according to

$$(m/A)^2 = 2k_p t \quad (2)$$

where m is the mass, A is the area, and t is the time. In **Figure 7–9**, the k_p values are shown, derived from the slope of all the collected long-term exposure data (Figure 4–6) for the different alloys at 650, 700, and 750 °C. The intersects were neglected and not set to zero, since a potential accelerated initial transient period is irrelevant for the long-term behavior, and the quality of the parabolic fits was much better using this approach.^[38]

For alloy 625, sufficient data at all three temperatures are available to determine the activation energy and thus temperature dependence from the Arrhenius plot shown in **Figure 10**.

Figure 7. k_p value of the different alloys at 650 °C.

Figure 8. k_p value of the different alloys at 700 °C.

Figure 9. k_p value of the different alloys at 750 °C.

Figure 10. Arrhenius Plot for alloy 625, based on the average k_p data.

In this plot, the \ln of the parabolic rate constants for weight gain are displayed as a function of the inverse temperature. The slope of the curve indicates an activation energy based on the assumption that the temperature dependence of k_p can be expressed as

$$k_p = A \exp(Q/RT) \quad (3)$$

where A is the pre-exponential factor for the reaction, R is the universal gas constant, and T is the absolute temperature (usually measured in kelvins). It should be noted that the Arrhenius activation energy term from the Arrhenius equation is an experimentally determined parameter that indicates the sensitivity of the oxidation rate to temperature and a single activated event. This activation energy is of $Q = 694 \pm 224 \text{ kJ mol}^{-1}$ about twice the value of literature data determined for air exposure, which is in the range of 250–300 kJ mol^{-1} for air exposure (recalculated based on $\text{mg}^2 \text{cm}^{-4} \text{s}^{-1}$ for comparison),^[39] indicating again that the thermal activation of the oxidation in CO_2 is slightly higher than in air for such alloys and temperatures as suggested by Pint and Pillai.^[40]

Even at the highest temperature of 750 °C, the k_p remains on average in the range of $10^{-14} \text{ g}^2 (\text{cm}^4 \text{s})^{-1}$, meaning less than 8.5 mg cm^{-2} weight gain after 100 000 h, which equals a scale thickness of around 16 μm , under the assumption of a chromia scale (density 5.22 g cm^{-3}). This corresponds to less than 8 μm of metal consumption in 100 000 h, suggesting that the corrosion rate, CR term, from CO_2 corrosion is negligible (considering wall thicknesses $>3 \text{ mm}$, so 8 μm is below 0.25% of the wall thickness). However, as discussed later, this oxide scale thickness and metal loss change might not directly reflect the change in mechanical stresses. It is essential to consider four main parameters regarding the target application. These parameters are discussed separately: temperature,^[39] pressure, CO_2 impurity level, and thermocycling.

2.2.2. Influence of Pressure on Corrosion

In contrast to other carbon-rich gases, for example, those causing metal dusting,^[41] the influence of pressure is not that high in CO_2 , at least not for the materials in question. The different Ni-based alloys and advanced austenitic steel Sanicro 25 do not show carburization at this low of a carbon activity, shown in Figure 8 for pure CO_2 at 25 and 0.1 MPa and CO_2 with 1% O_2 and 0.25% H_2O at ambient pressure and 25 MPa. In Figure 8, the k_p values in industrial grade CO_2 at various pressures and 750 °C were shown for alloy 617. Different alloys and steels were exposed at 750 °C at 0.1 and 30 MPa within the same experimental set-up at the same lab.^[42,43] From those studies, it becomes clear that the total CO_2 pressure is not a high-impact parameter, and the weight gain of Ni-based alloys such as 625 and 282 remains relatively insensitive to an increased pressure throughout the test duration of 5000 h or more.^[42,43] This generally low impact of the total pressure behavior was also confirmed by Oleksak et al.^[44] For completion, it should be mentioned that this does not apply to lower temperatures between 500 and 650 °C and lower grade steels, where a stronger pressure sensitivity has been reported.^[45]

2.2.3. Influence of Gas Purity on Corrosion

When the different weight gains are compared, gas purity can play a more prominent role.^[46] While many studies were conducted using research grade CO₂ (RG, 99.999%), when it comes to an industrial application in a power cycle, higher impurity levels are more reasonable and usually classified as industrial grade CO₂ (IG, ≈99.95%). On the other hand, comparing the different works shows that the differences between RG and IG CO₂ are not very high and within the scattering of the different tests. In contrast, higher impurities are generally always at the top of the weight gain for the various temperatures. When the fits are compared, the initial weight gains are higher, while the overall slopes of the curves are higher; thus, the later parabolic growth is not too affected. Especially for Fe-rich alloys at a pressure of 30 MPa and 750 °C, the impurities in s-CO₂ strongly increased the initial weight growth kinetics of AISI 310H and Sanicro 25.^[42] In **Figure 11**, it is shown that chromia evaporation becomes possible because of high impurities present in IG CO₂, which will enable chromium oxyhydroxide formation with higher p(CrO₂(OH)₂) at higher pressure. CrO₂(OH)₂ cannot form without these elements and significantly lower chromia evaporation as CrO₃ is expected in pure CO₂. This can explain the increased influence of the impurities at a higher pressure and at the beginning of the test when the outer scale forms.

Interestingly, Haynes 282 and alloy 740, with their higher aluminum and lower chromium contents, are also affected and form more internal alumina. This correlation between impurities and internal oxidation is best exemplified by the weight gain of the alloy CM 247 as reported by Pint and Unocic.^[37] This alloy is a cast alumina-forming superalloy, and when exposed to s-CO₂, the weight gain is very low. Still, it shows higher growth kinetics in the gas with higher impurities (H₂O and O₂). The explanation for this behavior might be found elsewhere, where it was shown that water vapor can change the necessary alloying element threshold for a protective alumina (sub-)scale.^[47] Impurities favor

Figure 11. Comparison of the partial pressures of the respective prevalent volatile Cr-species as a function of temperature calculated for pure CO₂ and CO₂ with 1% O₂ and 0.25% H₂O with FactSage 8.1 (FactPS database).

the internal oxidation of alloys that can form an outer alumina scale, e.g., in the absence of H₂O.^[48] CM 247 is a borderline alumina former and seems to lose its ability to form a protective alumina scale when impurities are present in CO₂, for Haynes 282 and alloy 740, internal oxidation proceeds faster. The advanced austenitic steels are also more affected by the presence of impurities in s-CO₂ than the Ni-based alloys.

2.2.4. Influence of Thermal Cycling on Corrosion

Finally, a key performance requirement in CSP plants is compliance with thermal cycling, which is always to be expected due to differences in incoming solar radiation and the day and night cycle. There will be some thermal fluctuation even if the location has a good solar resource and the HEX remains at relatively high temperatures most of the time due to the large thermal storage capacity. Thermal cycling induces stresses and thus can lead to oxide scale failure and spallation, affecting corrosion and erosion resistance. Austenitic and Ni-base alloys were tested thermocyclically in CO₂ at 10 h cycles to simulate such temperature changes and periodic cooldowns.^[43,49] The lab-scale thermocyclic exposure tests are usually not conducted under pressure due to technical challenges and are carried out only under atmospheric CO₂. Nevertheless, after an initial incubation, Sanicro 25 changed its behavior with highly increased kinetics and break-away oxidation.^[43,49] Among the Ni-based alloys, Haynes 282 and alloy 740 exhibited almost no influence from the thermocyclic exposure, whereas alloy 625 showed strongly increased spallation. It is also important to note that the thermo-cyclically exposed materials showed a high scatter in the weight change, and this scatter was wider for austenitic steels than Ni-based alloys. So, while a specific target may not be prescribed for the thermo-cyclic behavior, these studies show that the kinetics can be much faster than under isothermal conditions, and future testing in application-relevant cycles should be conducted since there is very little data currently available.^[43,49]

From this discussion of high-temperature corrosion in CO₂, it is evident that while the alloys of interest would seem to have high enough corrosion resistance for the application, there is still a need for additional data collection, especially concerning impurity influences and thermocyclic behavior. Additionally, at lower temperatures (500–650 °C), the high pressure of the s-CO₂ application eliminates lower-grade steels as a viable option for a multimaterial HEX from a corrosion standpoint.

2.3. Impact of CO₂ on the Mechanical Properties, Including Creep

The impact of CO₂ exposure on mechanical properties is more complex because microstructural changes can occur in the subsurface zone, e.g., due to selective depletion of scale-forming elements or internal oxidation or carburization, which will change the degradation over time and can also alter the mechanical properties as is discussed in the following. To the authors' best knowledge, there is only one published work that investigated the effect of s-CO₂ corrosion on the room temperature mechanical properties of steels and alloys after exposure to CO₂ gases.^[42] In this article, the yield strength of the

precipitation-strengthened Ni-base alloys 740 and CM 247 improved after exposure due to microstructural changes, which came at the expense of ductility.^[42] The yield strength of the other alloys investigated, 304, 310, and 740, was slightly affected, while the ductility was also significantly lowered.^[42] Thus, the currently available data on s-CO₂ exposure influence on room-temperature mechanical properties cannot eliminate or support any potential candidate materials. Interstitial C usually decreases ductility, and therefore, the room-temperature properties after s-CO₂ exposure need further investigation.

Depletion, metal loss, and microstructural changes from CO₂ exposure will significantly influence creep behavior and thus affect the high-temperature performance. For example, Pillai et al. investigated the subsurface changes after creep rupture of Haynes 282 specimens tested in air at 816 °C.^[50] They identified a predominant outer chromia scale with interspersed Ti-rich oxides. They also observed a similar subsurface depletion during high-temperature exposures in s-CO₂ of γ' -phase below the surface for Haynes 282 and alloy 740H. Al was mainly internally oxidized, and a γ' depletion zone was observed with a significant amount of η -phase (Ni₃Ti) as platelets. This is a critical finding since crack propagation was mainly observed in this γ' -depleted zone. Such microstructural changes will affect all potential materials, and additional studies are needed to address this complex interaction. By Pint et al. the internal oxidation was compared for different alloys and extrapolated to 100 000 h^[49] The intermetallic precipitation-strengthened alloys 740 and 282 showed much deeper internal oxidation zones with projected 23 and 37 μm depth than the solution-strengthened/carbide-reinforced material alloys 625, which, even after such long times, is predicted to be below 5 μm . As mentioned before for weight gain, the impurities in the CO₂ strongly affect the depth of internal oxidation. This highlights the need for further creep tests in CO₂, or of samples pre-exposed in CO₂, to fully answer the impact of CO₂ on the long-term mechanical (creep) properties. Especially for the precipitation-strengthened alloys, the metal loss, and the required corrosion allowance can thus differ from the values calculated from k_p .

2.4. Impact of Erosion on Corrosion Allowance

As previously mentioned, the external walls of the HEX tubes are exposed to air oxidation, erosion, and abrasion from heat-carrying particles, which will interact with oxidation. They can strongly influence metal wastage and, thus, corrosion/erosion allowance. Bauxite or the other particles planned for use are all hard ceramic particles. Depending on the design of the receiver, the particles cause impact erosion by impingement and surface abrasion resulting from the continuous movement of particles across surfaces. Various factors, including the hardness, roughness, and size of particles, and counterpart properties such as surface smoothness, material hardness, brittleness, ductility, and the relative movement of particle impact velocity and impact angle affect this erosion wear.^[51]

Unfortunately, very limited information about the erosion/abrasion of different HEX alloys at high temperatures has been published. However, some publications have dealt with receiver erosion, which can be leveraged here. Ho et al.^[52] performed

on-sun testing of high temperature falling particle receiver designs and reported severe degradation of stainless steel wire mesh structures used in the obstructed flow tests due to a combined effect of oxidation and surface wear after only 20 h of testing at 700 kW m⁻² irradiance, because a “chrome oxide shell formed that was abraded by the falling particles”. The particles impacted the mesh directly in that particular set-up, so the wear effect is much higher than in the planned HEX.

In one of the first laboratory tests of particle receiver erosion by Galiullin et al.^[53] the weight change of different alloys and steels was compared up to 750 °C. This is not as high as the outer wall temperature of about 900 °C targeted in the COMPASSCO₂ particle CSP design, and the operating conditions of the receiver are different than the HEX. In the receiver, the particles move at a much higher speed and also have the effect of direct concentrated solar irradiation. Additionally, the receiver is not under pressure. But even considering that, at 750 °C, the weight change after 216 h was concerningly high and about doubled compared to 650 °C.^[53] While the weight change was given in %, the micrographs show that the metal loss is about 300 μm for VM12 at 750 °C, which is even below alloys 617 and AISI 441 and at least one order of magnitude higher than the calculated metal loss due to oxidation in CO₂ (see previous section on kinetics). For alloy 617 severe erosion was already measured at 550 °C, while the other alloys (AISI 310, AISI 441, and VM12) showed little mass loss. The study results show that only the Co-based superalloy MAR-M-509 did not suffer significant weight reduction from erosion within the 500 h testing time at 750 °C. This superalloy has an exceptionally high amount of hard carbide phases in the microstructure and is somewhat similar to the Stellite materials, which are known for their good erosion resistance. Interestingly, in the same experiment, the austenitic Fe-based 310N and the ferritic-martensitic VM12 steel with a BCC structure showed higher erosion resistance than the tested Ni-based alloys and AISI 441.^[53]

Goel et al.^[54] investigated the behavior of alloy 740 and alloy 316 at 800 °C at a relative velocity of 3.5 cm s⁻¹. They found small weight change for alloy 740 of about 1 mg cm⁻² (which would correspond to about 2 μm /700 h for chromia), while alloy 316 showed severe weight loss of more than 20 mg cm⁻² after only 700 h, or roughly 40 μm in only 700 h for chromia.^[54] A linear extrapolation to 100 000 h (\approx 286 μm for alloy 740) shows the severity of this attack compared to the CO₂ corrosion (\approx 8 μm) on the inside of the HEX tubes. Goel et al.^[54] discuss what is abraded: oxide, parts of the scale, or metal, which depends on the actual conditions, such as the impact angle. The wear is more pronounced for bare metals at lower impingement angles below 30°. For more brittle coatings, the material loss increased with the contact angle between 0° and 90°.^[55] The oxide scales formed at high temperatures fall in the category of brittle materials, so the 90° angle is a very severe testing condition. The previously mentioned test by Galiullin et al. was conducted at a relatively low speed of 0.028 m s⁻¹, but the main specimen surface was oriented perpendicularly to the movement and faced a sintered-bauxite (\approx 1 mm) particle impact of nearly 90°, which provides some indication why the metal loss was so high.^[53]

Currently, the data available in the literature are still insufficient, and more investigations are required up to 900 °C to give values for the “erosion allowance” to predict HEX lifetime.

Simultaneously, the conditions for the design of the HEX must be better understood, such as the particle trajectory, local impact angles, and relative velocities, which should generally be lower compared to the receiver or other parts of the CSP plant operating with particles. This shows the requirement for simulations and long-term testing at various temperatures, which are necessary to understand the superimposed influences of oxidation, glazed oxide formation, oxide removal by erosion, and overall dependence on the ceramic particle contact angle, load, velocity, and chemistry. Additionally, hard coatings should be considered for the long-term stability of HEXs in particle CSP applications and to increase the resistance of the oxides that form since most substrates are somewhat prone to erosion at those temperatures. Various coatings have been suggested in.^[51] However, the combined high-temperature oxidation/erosion resistance remains a highly demanding material challenge—one that is critical for the lifetime of the particle/s-CO₂ heat exchangers.

3. Summary

Various commercially available, state-of-the-art Ni-based alloys and some advanced steels could meet the demanding requirements for a particle/s-CO₂ HEX tube material: 1) CO₂ corrosion under isothermal conditions is slow, and its influence on mechanical properties has already been investigated; 2) there are limited data on cyclic exposure in CO₂; and 3) the impact of a degraded subsurface zone on the long-term mechanical properties is not really understood.

The bigger question arises on the outside wall, where the surface is exposed to erosion: 1) the measured metal loss values are up to one order of magnitude higher than the metal loss on the inside of the tubes in contact with CO₂; 2) more data and better understanding are required since all discussed alloys are prone to erosion when the oxide is consumed; 3) materials with oxidation-resistant hard phases need to be developed, but such hard phases would simultaneously reduce the machinability of the alloys; 4) external hard coatings are likely the solution for the long-term stability of HEXs in particle/s-CO₂ CSP applications; and 5) these coatings must fulfill the complex requirements of high thermal conductivity, hardness, and applicability to Fe- and Ni-based tube materials.

Acknowledgements

This project had received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 958418 "COMPASsCO₂" (<https://www.compassco2.eu>).

Open Access funding enabled and organized by Projekt DEAL.

Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

Mathias Christian Galetz: conceptualization (equal); funding acquisition (equal); resources (lead); writing—original draft (lead). **Emma Marie Hamilton White:** conceptualization (equal); project administration (equal);

writing—original draft (supporting). **Michael Kerbstadt:** data curation (supporting); formal analysis (equal); visualization (lead); writing—review and editing (supporting). **Clara Schlereth:** formal analysis (equal); methodology (supporting); writing—review and editing (equal). **Xabier Montero:** conceptualization (equal); writing—original draft (supporting). **Daniel Benitez:** funding acquisition (lead); project administration (lead); resources (equal); writing—review and editing (equal).

Keywords

concentrated solar thermal power, erosion, heat exchanger, material selection, s-CO₂ corrosion

Received: September 10, 2024

Revised: February 4, 2025

Published online: April 18, 2025

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